
Cardinality, Simplex and Proximal Operator*

Alberto De Marchi
Bundeswehr University Munich
alberto.demarchi@unibw.de

Abstract

In this report, we consider the proximal operator for the ℓ_0 “norm”, which is widely adopted as a sparsity-inducing penalty in e.g. compressed sensing, sparse signal representation and cardinality or cardinality-constrained optimization. Analytical expressions for the unconstrained and the nonnegative proximal point are found. Then, motivated by applications in mixed-integer optimal control, we develop a numerical method tailored for evaluating the simplex-constrained proximal operator. We present numerical investigations which demonstrate the effectiveness of the method, in terms of computation time and complexity. Also, we discuss the scaled proximal operator, arising in proximal Newton-type methods, and evaluate it via an accelerated first-order proximal method.

1 Introduction

As datasets become larger, measurement rates increase and energy consumption is to be controlled, the interest in compressed sensing and sparse representation of signals is growing. These ideas are strictly related to the Ockham’s razor, or principle of parsimony [1], stating that the simplest solution to a problem should be preferred. This parsimony may be achieved by encouraging sparse representations for a given phenomenon or sparse solutions for a given problem. In this context, the number of nonzero elements of a vector, i.e. its cardinality, plays a key role. In fact, sparse optimization techniques can be exploited for both cardinality-constrained [2] and cardinality optimization problems [3]. However, due to its nonconvexity and (jump) discontinuities, its numerical treatment is troublesome. It turns out that other sparsity-inducing penalties are more amenable to numerical methods, e.g. the ℓ_1 -norm [1]. On the other hand, these may not yield comparable results if the proportion of nonzero elements is not small enough [4]. In this work, we consider the ℓ_0 -penalty and focus on evaluating its proximal operator. This is the basic operation for solving an optimization problem via proximal algorithms, which are a tool for nonsmooth, constrained, large-scale optimization problems [5, 6, 7]. For a detailed overview on proximal algorithms refer to [8]. We point out that this work arises from an application in the field of automatic control, in particular in mixed-integer optimal control with switching costs, through variable time transformation and switching time optimization [9, 10]. Motivated by this application, we are interested in evaluating the proximal operator for the ℓ_0 function, defined as the number of nonzero elements of a vector, namely

$$(1) \quad \ell_0(\mathbf{x}) := |\{i \mid x_i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}|, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Many authors abuse terminology by referring to ℓ_0 as a norm; however, this is not a norm because it is not homogeneous. Despite these defects as a mathematical norm, the non-zero counting “norm” has uses in scientific computing and signal processing, as mentioned above, e.g. in compressed sensing. Induced by its close relation to norms, we also denote $\ell_0(\mathbf{x}) = \|\mathbf{x}\|_0$. Hence, the proximal operator for the ℓ_0 function reads [8, 6]

$$(2) \quad \text{prox}_\alpha(\mathbf{x}) := \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{F}} \left\{ \alpha \|\mathbf{y}\|_0 + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}\|_2^2 \right\}$$

*Date: July 14, 2019. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3334538](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3334538).

where $\alpha \geq 0$ is a nonnegative scalar and \mathcal{F} denotes the feasible set for the proximal point. Typically it is assumed $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}^n$, yielding an unconstrained yet nonconvex problem [8, 6, 7]. In contrast, driven by the aforementioned application, we are also interested in the nonnegative case and the simplex-constrained case, namely respectively with $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^n$ and $\mathcal{F} = \Delta$ in (2). Herein, the set \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^n denotes the set of real vectors with nonnegative entries and the set Δ denotes the n -simplex, that is $\Delta := \{\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \mathbf{d} \geq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{d} = \beta, \beta \geq 0\}$. Some assumptions are considered in the following.

Assumption 1. (i) Scalar α is positive, i.e. $\alpha > 0$. (ii) Scalar β is positive, i.e. $\beta > 0$. (iii) Input vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is sorted, i.e. $x_1 \leq x_2 \leq \dots \leq x_n$.

Nevertheless, these are very weak assumptions and do not affect the following developments and results.

Remark 1. (i) For $\alpha = 0$, the problem in (2) turns into a linearly-constrained least-squares problem, that is a standard quadratic program. (ii) For $\beta = 0$, the feasible set collapses to the origin, i.e. it is $\mathcal{F} = \Delta = \{\mathbf{0}\}$, and thus the solution is trivially the origin. (iii) The proximal operator for the ℓ_0 function is invariant under permutation of the input vector and reverse-permutation of the output vector. This is numerically inefficient though.

We briefly report results from the literature for the unconstrained case, which is considered in several packages [11, 12, 13]. These results are then extended to the nonnegative case. Notice that for both these cases the proximal point can be expressed analytically and the computation can be performed entrywise in that the optimization problem is separable. In fact, for a given input vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and scalar $\alpha \geq 0$, the cost function $\Pi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ can be written as $\Pi(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \pi(y_i)$, with

$$(3) \quad \pi(y_i) := \alpha \|y_i\|_0 + 1/2(y_i - x_i)^2,$$

for any $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, see (2). Instead, for the simplex-constrained proximal point, there is a coupling among entries due to the linear equality constraint and thus entrywise optimization is not possible; also, no simple expression has been found yet. Furthermore, we highlight that all these problems do not admit a unique global solution in general, due to the intrinsic nonconvexity of ℓ_0 .

This contribution is organized as follows. Sections 2 and 3 deal with the unconstrained and the nonnegative problem, respectively. The simplex-constrained problem is discussed in Section 4, and a solution method is proposed. Numerical investigations are reported in Section 5 and commented. Section 6 concludes the report and delineates future research directions.

2 Unconstrained Proximal Point

Consider the unconstrained proximal operator, namely problem (2) with feasible set $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}^n$, and denote \mathbf{y}^* a solution. The entrywise cost can be expressed, based on (3), as

$$(4) \quad \pi(y_i) = \begin{cases} 1/2 x_i^2 & \text{if } y_i = 0, \\ \alpha + 1/2(y_i - x_i)^2 & \text{if } y_i \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

In the case $y_i \neq 0$, the minimum cost is α , with $y_i = x_i$. Then, entrywise minimization yields

$$(5) \quad y_i^* = \arg \min_{y_i} \pi(y_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |x_i| < \sqrt{2\alpha}, \\ \{0, x_i\} & \text{if } |x_i| = \sqrt{2\alpha}, \\ x_i & \text{if } |x_i| > \sqrt{2\alpha}. \end{cases}$$

Hence, solution is not unique in general; uniqueness can be guaranteed by, e.g., prioritizing sparsity, namely choosing $y_i^* = 0$ if $|x_i| \leq \sqrt{2\alpha}$ and $y_i^* = x_i$ if $|x_i| > \sqrt{2\alpha}$.

3 Nonnegative Proximal Point

Consider the nonnegative proximal operator, namely problem (2) with feasible set $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^n$, and denote \mathbf{y}^* a solution. The entrywise cost can be expressed, based on (3), as

$$(6) \quad \pi_i = \begin{cases} 1/2 x_i^2 & \text{if } y_i = 0, \\ \alpha + 1/2(y_i - x_i)^2 & \text{if } y_i > 0. \end{cases}$$

In the case $y_i > 0$, the minimum cost is α , with $y_i = x_i$. Then, entrywise minimization yields

$$(7) \quad y_i^* = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x_i < \sqrt{2\alpha}, \\ \{0, x_i\} & \text{if } x_i = \sqrt{2\alpha}, \\ x_i & \text{if } x_i > \sqrt{2\alpha}. \end{cases}$$

Hence, again, solution is not unique in general; uniqueness can be guaranteed by, e.g., prioritizing sparsity, namely choosing $y_i^* = 0$ if $x_i \leq \sqrt{2\alpha}$ and $y_i^* = x_i$ if $x_i > \sqrt{2\alpha}$.

4 Simplex-Constrained Proximal Point

Consider the simplex-constrained proximal operator, namely problem (2) with feasible set $\mathcal{F} = \Delta$, and denote \mathbf{y}^* a solution. As mentioned above, this problem is not separable in that the entries of \mathbf{y}^* are coupled through the simplex constraint, namely $\mathbf{y}^* \in \Delta$, i.e. $\mathbf{y}^* \geq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{y}^* = \beta$. Hence, a different approach is adopted compared to the one followed in previous Sections. Let us reformulate the simplex-constrained problem in terms of the number of zero elements, denoted m , in a vector \mathbf{y} . In [4] the authors adopt a similar idea but propose a different method for a different problem. Introducing the integer variable m , problem (2) can be viewed as a constrained mixed-integer quadratic program, and can be solved as such, but we seek a tailored method exploiting the problem structure. In our approach, problem (2) is interpreted as and associated to a bilevel program, aiming at optimizing the number of zero elements m , at the upper level, while accounting for the positive entries of \mathbf{y} at the lower level. From this perspective, the latter is a simplex-constrained least-squares problem and, as such, it admits an unique global solution; thus, the bilevel program is equivalent to the original problem [14].

The integer scalar m takes values in $\mathcal{M}_o := \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ for any positive scalar β ; for $\beta = 0$, trivially it is $\mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{0}$ and hence $m^* = n$. In fact, for some values of m , there might be no lower level solution with such number of zero elements; hence, variable m may be allowed to take values only in a subset $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{M}_o$. In the following, by inspecting the lower level problem and solution procedure, we identify a feasibility criterion to find the feasible set \mathcal{M} . Also, an analytical expression for the solution vector and its associated cost is found. Let us define the set Δ_m consisting of vectors in the simplex Δ with m zero entries, namely $\Delta_m := \{\mathbf{d} \in \Delta \mid \|\mathbf{d}\|_0 = n - m\}$. Then, for any $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the lower level problem reads

$$(8) \quad \mathbf{y}^*(m) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \Delta_m} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}\|_2^2 \right\}$$

and its solution $\mathbf{y}^*(m)$ has a specific structure.

Lemma 1. *Consider any integer scalar $m \in \mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{M}_o$ and any vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ sorted in ascending order. Then, there exists an unique vector $\mathbf{y}^*(m)$ solving problem (8). This vector has m initial zero entries, i.e. $y_i^*(m) = 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$, followed by $(n - m)$ positive entries, i.e. $y_i^*(m) > 0$ for $i = m + 1, \dots, n$.*

Proof. Existence and uniqueness are obtained because, for any given feasible m , problem (8) is a quadratic program with linear constraints. The solution structure follows from the assumption on vector \mathbf{x} and the simplex constraint. ■

Let us denote L the Lagrange function for the lower level problem and λ the multiplier associated to the equality constraint in the simplex, i.e. $\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{y} = \beta$. Omitting constraints for nonnegativity and number of zero elements, to be checked *a posteriori*, the Lagrange function reads

$$(9) \quad L(\mathbf{y}, \lambda) := \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}\|_2^2 + \lambda(\beta - \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{y}).$$

First-order necessary optimality conditions for problem (8) are also sufficient, thanks to convexity. Direct derivation of L in (9) with respect to \mathbf{y} , considering Lemma 1 and m zero entries, $m \in \mathcal{M}$, yields

$$(10) \quad y_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \\ x_i + \lambda & \text{if } i \in \{m + 1, \dots, n\}. \end{cases}$$

Then, substituting this result into the equality constraint, after some rearrangements, one obtain an expression for the multiplier λ as dependent solely on m , namely

$$(11) \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{n-m} \left(\beta - \sum_{i=m+1}^n x_i \right)$$

The nonnegativity constraints are not enforced so far. However, given a vector \mathbf{x} , for any $m \in \mathcal{M}_\circ$, the associated multiplier λ is fixed by (11) and thus one can check whether the vector \mathbf{y} from (10) has negative entries or not. Given m , it suffices to check $y_{m+1} = x_{m+1} + \lambda > 0$, because \mathbf{x} is sorted and hence it holds $y_{m+1} \leq y_{m+2} \leq \dots \leq y_n$. If this conditions is not met, the tested value of m is actually not feasible, i.e. $m \notin \mathcal{M}$.

Remark 2. *It may be possible to prune some values for m by solving problem (2) with $\alpha = 0$, which reduces to a simplex-constrained least-squares problem. Denote m_0 the number of zero elements in its solution vector. Then, the number of zero elements m in a vector solving problem (2) is at least m_0 , namely it holds $m \geq m_0$, for any $\alpha \geq 0$.*

For each and every feasible $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the lower level solution $\mathbf{y}^*(m)$ reads as in (10), where the multiplier $\lambda = \lambda(m)$ is given in (11). The feasible set \mathcal{M} for m can be defined as

$$(12) \quad \mathcal{M} := \{m \mid m \in \mathcal{M}_\circ \wedge x_{m+1} + \lambda(m) > 0\}.$$

Then, for every $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the associated cost $c : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as $c(m) := \Pi(\mathbf{y}^*(m))$ and yields

$$(13) \quad \begin{aligned} c(m) &= \alpha \|\mathbf{y}^*(m)\|_0 + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}^*(m) - \mathbf{x}\|_2^2 \\ &= \alpha(n-m) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^m x_j^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=m+1}^n \lambda^2(m) \\ &= \alpha(n-m) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^m x_j^2 + \frac{1}{2} (n-m) \lambda^2(m) \end{aligned}$$

Once the cost $c(m)$ is associated to every $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the minimum c^* is searched, a corresponding minimizer m^* retrieved, and then $\mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{y}^*(m^*)$. This method, based on a sort of extensive search, was conceived for small-sized problems; nevertheless, as pointed out in [Section 5](#), it performs and scales relatively well to mid-scale problems too.

Remark 3. *Numerical evaluation of λ and c for different values of m can be performed more efficiently by storing the cumulative sums in (11) and (13).*

Another observation can be exploited to determine the feasible set \mathcal{M} .

Lemma 2. *Consider $\beta > 0$. Then, the feasible set can be expressed as $\mathcal{M} = \{m \in \mathcal{M}_\circ \mid m \geq m_l\}$. The value of m_l depends on \mathbf{x} and β , and corresponds to the lowest value $m \in \mathcal{M}_\circ$ such that $x_{m+1} + \lambda(m) > 0$.*

Proof. Define feasibility function $\phi(m) := x_{m+1} + \lambda(m)$. Hence, by definition, it holds $m \in \mathcal{M} \Leftrightarrow m \in \mathcal{M}_\circ \wedge \phi(m) > 0$. Consider any $p, q \in \mathcal{M}_\circ$, with $p < q$ and p feasible, namely $p \in \mathcal{M}$, and hence $\phi(p) > 0$. We seek a proof that q is feasible, that is, $\phi(q) > 0$. Based on (11) and the definition of ϕ , it holds

$$(14) \quad \phi(q) = x_{q+1} + \frac{1}{(n-q)} \left(\beta - \sum_{j=q+1}^n x_j \right).$$

Expanding and rearranging the terms to collect $\phi(p)$ yield

$$(15) \quad \phi(q) = x_{q+1} + \frac{(n-p)}{(n-q)} [\phi(p) - x_{p+1}] + \frac{1}{(n-q)} \sum_{j=p+1}^q x_j.$$

A lower bound on the last term is obtained by observing that it holds $\sum_{j=p+1}^q x_j \geq (q-p)x_{p+1}$, thanks to (iii) in [Assumption 1](#). Hence, it follows

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(q) &\geq x_{q+1} + \frac{(n-p)}{(n-q)} [\phi(p) - x_{p+1}] + \frac{(q-p)}{(n-q)} x_{p+1} \\ &\geq x_{q+1} + \frac{(n-p)}{(n-q)} \phi(p) - x_{p+1} \\ &\geq \frac{n-p}{n-q} \phi(p) > \phi(p) > 0. \quad \blacksquare\end{aligned}$$

Finally, we notice that cost function $c : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined above, is convex (proof: it is the sum of two nonnegative convex functions). This property is not considered in the solution method proposed above, but one could take advantage of it in order to further exploit the problem structure for dealing with large-scale problems. In fact, the upper level problem is a single-, integer, bounded variable convex problem. We actually implemented an algorithm conceived for such problems, based on Brent's method [15] and revised to manage an integer variable. As mentioned in [Section 5](#), this did not perform consistently better than the extensive search in the aforementioned approach.

Algorithm 1 Simplex-constrained ℓ_0 proximal point.

```

procedure PROX_L0_SIMPLEX( $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n, \alpha \geq 0, \beta \geq 0$ )
2:   if  $\beta = 0$  then
       $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 
4:   return  $\mathbf{y}$ 
      end if
6:    $\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{P} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\mathbf{x})$  ▷ Sorting,  $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{x}$ 
       $\mathcal{M}_o \leftarrow \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ 
8:   for  $m \in \mathcal{M}_o$  do
       $\lambda_m \leftarrow (\beta - \sum_{i=m+1}^n x_i) / (n-m)$  ▷ Multiplier, Eq. Eq. \(11\)
10:  end for
       $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \{m \mid m \in \mathcal{M}_o \wedge \hat{x}_{m+1} + \lambda_m > 0\}$  ▷ Feasible set, Eq. Eq. \(12\)
12:  for  $m \in \mathcal{M}$  do
       $c_m \leftarrow (n-m)(\alpha + 1/2\lambda_m^2) + 1/2 \sum_{i=1}^m x_i^2$  ▷ Cost, Eq. Eq. \(13\)
14:  end for
       $m^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} c_m$  ▷ Minimizer
16:   $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 
      for  $i \in \{m^* + 1, \dots, n\}$  do
18:     $\hat{y}_i \leftarrow \hat{x}_i + \lambda_{m^*}$  ▷ Eq. Eq. \(10\)
      end for
20:   $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \mathbf{P}^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{y}}$  ▷ Re-ordering
      return  $\mathbf{y}$ 
22: end procedure

```

5 Numerical Results

In this section, we first evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed numerical method for evaluating the proximal operator of the ℓ_0 function, in the unconstrained, nonnegative and simplex-constrained case. Then, the scaled proximal operator is introduced and briefly discussed. Considering dense scaling matrices, we evaluate the scaled ℓ_0 proximal operator by solving the underlying optimization problem through an accelerated first-order proximal method, taking advantage of the available ℓ_0 proximal operator.

The source code used to produce the numerical results of this publication is available on Zenodo at doi:[10.5281/zenodo.2567457](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567457). All examples are implemented in MATLAB 2018b and run on Ubuntu 16.04, with Intel Core i7-8700 3,2 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. The problem instances are (pseudo)randomly generated; in the following, $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ denotes the Gaussian distribution with mean value μ and variance σ^2 , and $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ denotes the uniform distribution in the interval $[a, b]$.

5.1 Proximal Operator

We solve problem (2) with feasible set \mathbb{R}^n , \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^n and Δ . The problem size n ranges between 10 and 10^8 , and each instance consists of a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $x_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, a scalar $\alpha \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ and a scalar $\beta \sim \mathcal{U}(0, n)$. For each problem size, $m = 100$ test instances are generated and solved.

Figure 1: Evaluating the ℓ_0 proximal operator: CPU time. 100 instances per problem size, mean value (dot), median value (solid line), 0.25–0.75 quantiles (filled region), 0.09–0.91 quantiles (dashed line).

The proposed method for the simplex-constrained ℓ_0 proximal operator exhibits quasilinear time complexity, see Fig. 1. However, it is approximately 100 times slower than unconstrained and nonnegative proximal point evaluations; the latter is slightly faster than the former. Even though the proposed method was originally designed for small-sized problem instances, it turns out to perform consistently better than another method conceived for larger-scale problems and mentioned in Section 4. We argue this is heavily due to sorting and re-ordering operations, needed to have a sorted input vector, see (iii) in Assumption 1. In fact, significant time is spent for these operations, especially for sorting; in our investigations, these required about $\frac{1}{3}$ to $\frac{2}{3}$ (for larger instances) of the overall computation time. Hence, we argue the proposed method can be easily outperformed by novel ones not requiring these operations.

5.2 Scaled Proximal Operator

Let us consider the scaled proximal operator arising in proximal Newton-type methods [5, 6]. For the ℓ_0 function, it reads

$$\text{prox}_{\alpha}^{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{x}) := \arg \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{F}} \left\{ \alpha \|\mathbf{y}\|_0 + \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x})^{\top} \mathbf{H} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) \right\}$$

where the scaling matrix \mathbf{H} can be assumed symmetric positive definite [5, 6]. As for problem (2), there is not an unique solution in general. For a constant diagonal $\mathbf{H} = \gamma \mathbf{I}$, the scaled problem reduces to (2) and is often adopted because it leads to inexpensive proximal iterations. On the other hand, more general matrices \mathbf{H} may lead to time-consuming proximal operators; in fact, the choice of \mathbf{H} remains very much an art [6]. Different choices of \mathbf{H} yield several algorithms, ranging from e.g. iterative soft thresholding to proximal Newton method, and a trade-off between the number and the computational cost of each proximal iteration arises [5, 6].

Here, we treat the scaled ℓ_0 proximal operator as a composite problem amenable to proximal algorithms. We evaluate it by means of a fast proximal gradient method [8]. In particular, we adopt the `fista` routine provided by the publicly available FOM package [7]; default options are used: non-monotonic method with backtracking, `maxiter`= 1000, `eps`= 10^{-5} . The problem size n ranges between 10 and 10^4 , and each instance consists of a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $x_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, a nonnegative scalar $\alpha \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$, a nonnegative scalar $\beta \sim \mathcal{U}(0, n)$ and a matrix $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{Q}^{\top} \mathbf{Q}$, where $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $q_{ij} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. For sparse problems, matrix $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is generated by the `sprandn` MATLAB’s routine, with density equal to $3/n$. Input vector \mathbf{x} is considered also as initial guess. For each problem size, $m = 100$ test instances are generated and solved.

Figure 2: Evaluating the scaled ℓ_0 proximal operator, dense scaling: (a) CPU time and (b) iterations. 100 instances per problem size, mean value (dot), median value (solid line), 0.25–0.75 quantiles (filled region), 0.09–0.91 quantiles (dashed line).

Results in terms computation time and iterations taken by `fista` are reported in Figs. 2 and 3, for dense and sparse problems, respectively. First of all, we notice that the number of iterations seems to increase linearly with the problem size, and then saturates at the maximal number, see Figs. 2b and 3b. For both, dense and sparse cases, the more constrained the problem is, the fewer iterations are needed for a given problem size; this is significantly more accentuated for dense problems. In terms of CPU time, there are only minor differences for small-scale problems, approximately up to $n \approx 10^3$, see Figs. 2a and 3a. A linear relationship between problem size and CPU time is observed, for sparse problems, over the whole range under investigation; instead, for dense problems, quadratic, or even super-quadratic, growth appears after a kink at about $n \approx 10^3$. We underline that a direct comparison of Figs. 2a and 3a with Fig. 1 is not fair, in that first-order proximal methods typically requires far more iterations to converge [8, 5, 6]. Hence, especially for small-scale problem, proximal Newton-type methods may be competitive with first-order methods.

Figure 3: Evaluating the scaled ℓ_0 proximal operator, sparse scaling: (a) CPU time and (b) iterations. 100 instances per problem size, mean value (dot), median value (solid line), 0.25–0.75 quantiles (filled region), 0.09–0.91 quantiles (dashed line).

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this report, we have presented a bilevel approach for evaluating the proximal operator of the ℓ_0 “norm” with nonnegativity and simplex constraints. The proposed numerical method has been tested and it exhibits quasilinear time complexity. Also, we have investigated its suitability for dealing with the scaled ℓ_0 proximal operator, which typically is a costly subproblem in proximal Newton-type methods.

Future research may focus on efficient algorithms for larger-scale problems as well as on structure exploitation in evaluating the scaled proximal operator. Further applications may be addressed for both, signal processing and automatic control.

References

- [1] F. Bach, R. Jenatton, J. Mairal, and G. Obozinski, “Optimization with sparsity-inducing penalties,” *Foundations and Trends® in Machine Learning*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–106, 2012.
- [2] O. Burdakov, C. Kanzow, and A. Schwartz, “On a reformulation of mathematical programs with cardinality constraints,” in *Advances in Global Optimization*, D. Gao, N. Ruan, and W. Xing, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 3–14.
- [3] M. Feng, J. E. Mitchell, J.-S. Pang, X. Shen, and A. Wächter, “Complementarity formulations of ℓ_0 -norm optimization problems,” *Pacific Journal of Optimization*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 273–305, 2018.
- [4] L. Mancera and J. Portilla, “L0-norm-based sparse representation through alternate projections,” in *2006 International Conference on Image Processing*, Oct 2006, pp. 2089–2092.
- [5] J. D. Lee, Y. Sun, and M. A. Saunders, “Proximal Newton-type methods for minimizing composite functions,” *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 1420–1443, 2014.
- [6] M. P. Friedlander and G. Goh, “Efficient evaluation of scaled proximal operators,” *Electronic Transactions on Numerical Analysis*, vol. 46, pp. 1–22, 2017.
- [7] A. Beck and N. Guttman-Beck, “FOM – a MATLAB toolbox of first-order methods for solving convex optimization problems,” *Optimization Methods and Software*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 172–193, 2019.
- [8] N. Parikh and S. Boyd, “Proximal algorithms,” *Foundations and Trends® in Optimization*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 127–239, 2014.
- [9] M. Gerds, “A variable time transformation method for mixed-integer optimal control problems,” *Optimal Control Applications and Methods*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 169–182, 2006.
- [10] A. De Marchi, “On the mixed-integer linear-quadratic optimal control with switching cost,” *IEEE Control Systems Letters*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 990–995, Oct 2019.
- [11] N. Perraudin, V. Kalofolias, D. Shuman, and P. Vandergheynst, “UNLocBoX: a MATLAB convex optimization toolbox using proximal-splitting methods,” 2016, arXiv:1402.0779.
- [12] G. Chierchia, E. Chouzenoux, P. L. Combettes, and J.-C. Pesquet, “The proximity operator repository. User’s guide.” [Online]. Available: <http://proximity-operator.net/download/guide.pdf>
- [13] L. Stella, N. Antonello, and M. Fält, “ProximalOperators.jl - Proximal operators for nonsmooth optimization in Julia.” [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/kul-forbes/ProximalOperators.jl>
- [14] S. Dempe, *Foundations of Bilevel Programming*, ser. Nonconvex Optimization and Its Applications. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2002, vol. 61.
- [15] R. P. Brent, *Algorithms for Minimization without Derivatives*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1973.